

108-134 d, primarily because of delayed flowering (see table). The maturity of medium-duration varieties (125 to 140 d) was not extended.

Extended duration differed among varieties. The differences in maturity in short-duration varieties could not be associated with their expected duration. Duration of 113-d Cul. 1954 was extended by 9 d, that of 108-d Cul. 25337 by 26 d. The capacity to extend the growth period, and thereby the duration, could be a varietal character independent of actual duration.

Grain yield was independent of duration. Cul. 4, MO.5, Karthika, and Jyothi had high yields; Cul. 126, Cul. 43-1-4, Cul. 25331, Bhagya, and Onam, low yields. Panicles/hill and 1,000-grain weight showed a similar trend. The drought stress experienced in the nursery might have persisted after transplanting in some varieties, while other varieties recovered during subsequent growth. Varieties capable of adjusting duration could be recommended for conditions when a delay in transplanting can be anticipated. □

Days to 50% flowering, duration, panicles/hill, 1000-grain weight, and grain yield of cultures and varieties. Kerala, India, 1983 wet season.

Culture or variety	Days to 50% flowering	Seed-to-seed duration (d)			Panicles (no./hill)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
		Normal	In the experiment	Extended			
Cul. 169	116	142	146	4	9.4	28.0	1.9
Cul. 4	112	140	142	2	10.1	36.7	3.2
Cul. 126	108	138	138	0	8.9	33.6	1.6
Jaya	110	135	140	5	8.3	34.6	2.2
MO. 5	104	120	134	14	11.9	34.0	3.0
MO. 6	104	120	134	14	7.0	29.6	2.0
Jyothi	98	115	128	13	7.3	32.4	2.8
Cul. 1954	92	113	122	9	10.8	25.8	1.8
Karthika	105	110	135	25	9.9	32.9	2.9
Cul. 25331	99	108	129	21	8.2	39.2	1.7
Cul. 25337	104	108	134	26	8.2	35.0	2.4
Swarnaprabha	101	108	131	23	7.3	32.1	2.4
Bhagya	80	100	110	10	6.1	35.0	1.5
Onam	80	95	110	15	7.1	34.8	1.7
Cul. 43-1-4	78	95	108	13	5.9	34.6	1.2
LSD (0.05)	4	—	4	—	2.5	1.4	0.8

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Effect of planting date, seedling age, and planting density on late planted wet season rice

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Delayed rains necessitate transplanting overage seedlings in many rainfed rice-growing areas of India. Other constraints to timely transplanting are delayed delivery of canal water and nonavailability of agricultural labor.

We studied the effect of planting date, seedling age, and planting density in a split-plot design during the 1983 and 1984 wet seasons. Soil was a sandy loam of Mahanadi delta, with pH 6.5, cation exchange capacity 11 meq/ 100 g. The water table fluctuated from 10 cm to 40 cm deep. Rice variety CR1018 (155 d duration) was transplanted at

Table 1. Grain yield of CR1018 as influenced by transplanting date, seedling age, and spacing. Cuttack, India, 1983 wet season.

Planting date	Seedling (d)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha) at given spacing				Mean yield (t/ha)
		15 × 15 cm (44)	20 × 15 cm (33)	20 × 20 cm (25)	25 × 20 cm (20)	
15 Jul	30	5.3	5.8	6.1	5.7	5.7
15 Aug	30	4.4	5.1	4.8	4.4	4.6
15 Aug	60	3.7	4.6	4.4	4.4	4.2
15 Sep	30	2.3	2.6	1.9	2.2	3.0
15 Sep	60	3.5	3.3	2.4	3.1	2.9
Mean		3.8	4.3	3.9	3.9	
LSD (0.05) main plot (planting date × seedling age)				—	0.4	
Subplot (spacing)				—	0.4	
Interaction				—	ns	

^aNumbers in parentheses give the plant population/m².

populations of 20,25, 33, and 44 hills/ m².

Grain yield was reduced 18% with mid-Aug transplanting and 44% with mid-Sep in 1983, and 22% and 44%, respectively, in 1984 (Table 1, 2). Using

30- or 60-d-old seedlings did not affect mid-Aug transplanting yield; 60-d-old seedlings were significantly superior to 30-d-old seedlings with mid-Sep transplanting. Spacing seedlings 20 × 15 cm was optimum. □

Table 2. Grain yield of CR1018 as influenced by transplanting date, seedling age, and spacing. Cuttack, India, 1984 wet season.

Spacing (cm)	Seedling age (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)			Mean yield (t/ha)
		15 Jul	15 Aug	15 Sep	
15 × 15	30	5.5	4.9	2.8	4.4
	60	3.9	4.0	3.4	3.8
20 × 15	30	5.2	3.5	2.7	3.8
	60	5.5	4.1	3.3	4.3
20 × 20	30	5.3	4.0	2.6	4.0
	60	5.2	3.9	3.2	4.1
25 × 20	30	5.4	3.9	2.2	3.8
	60	5.3	3.8	2.9	4.0
Mean		5.2	4.0	2.9	
LSD (0.05)	main plot (planting dates)	=		1.0	
LSD (0.05)	subplot (spacing × seedling age)	=		ns	
LSD (0.05)	for comparing planting dates (spacing × seedling age)	=		1.1	
LSD (0.05)	for comparing (spacing × seedling age) within a planting date	=		0.8	

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Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Response of BR3 rice to duckweed (*Lemna minor*) application

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Duckweed is a minute, diploid spore-producing, vascular, free-floating aquatic plant that contains around 4% N. It grows abundantly in stagnant

water in Bangladesh, especially during the monsoon. We studied its use as an organic N source for rice.

Duckweed was grown in earthen pots 56.41 cm in diameter (1 m²), filled with 60 kg air-dried soil and 72 liters of water. Composition (oven-dried basis) of the duckweed was 4.2% N; 2.3% P; 3.02% K; and 29.64% organic C.

Two seedlings of rice variety BR3 were planted in pots containing 10 kg soil and fertilized with 35 kg P and 33 kg K/ha. Soil was silty loam with pH 5.2, 0.84% organic C, 80 kg 2M KCl

extractable N/ha, 18.4 kg Olsen's reagent extractable P/ha, and 134 kg neutral N ammonium acetate extractable K/ha.

Treatments were 5 t fresh duckweed/ha = 833 kg oven-dried duckweed/ha, and 5.0, 2.5, 1.9, and 1.43 t oven-dried duckweed/ha and 2 combinations of oven-dried duckweed + urea. Each treatment was replicated three times in a completely randomized design.

Incorporating 5 t oven-dried duckweed/ha increased grain yields 52% and straw yields 50% (see table). Combined 20 kg urea N/ha + 1.43 t duckweed/ha increased grain yields 62% and straw yields 67%. Urea applied at 80 kg N/ha increased grain yields 50% and straw yields 44%. Oven-dried duckweed at 5 t/ha was better than urea at 80 kg N/ha.

N uptake was greater in the treatments where urea was applied. □

Yield of and N uptake by BR3 rice as affected by application of duckweed and urea.

t/ha	Duckweed applied		Urea applied (kg N/ha)	Yield (g/pot)		N uptake (mg/pot)
	kg N/ha	As % weight of 10 kg soil		Grain	Straw	
0	0	0	0	8.51	7.21	140.4
5.00 ^a	35	0.250	0	9.80	7.31	165.1
5.00	210	0.250	0	13.00	10.82	279.4
2.50	105	0.125	0	12.01	8.55	235.9
1.90	80	0.095	0	12.40	10.00	251.1
1.43	60	0.070	0	11.94	9.77	225.6
1.43	60	0.070	20	13.80	12.11	318.3
0.95	40	0.048	40	13.50	11.28	313.1
0.00	0	0.000	80	12.80	10.42	327.8
LSD (P=0.01)				2.36	1.11	

^aFresh duckweed incorporated 7 d before transplanting.

Using iron pyrite to increase nitrogen efficiency in rice under sodic conditions

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N efficiency in rice under sodic conditions is reduced because of heavy